

Scattering Reactions versus Configurations in Generalized Statistical Mechanics

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Regular statistical mechanics makes use of the idea of configurations which are closely related to the canonical and grand canonical partition functions. In fact, in (1) a factorial counting approach is shown to lead directly to the $\exp(-E/T)$ canonical partition function weight. In a number of previous notes, we have argued one may use time reversal elastic scattering balance to obtain the Maxwell-Boltzmann (MB), Fermi-Dirac (FD) and Bose-Einstein (BE) distributions without any counting, partition functions or entropy. In (2), we tried to show how the scattering approach for the MB case may map into a counting and hence partition scheme. For generalized cases, however, with correlations between particles, we still apply the scattering approach, but it no longer seems to map to configurations. Thus, “summing” over configurations, say in a grand canonical partition, may be problematic. In this note, we try to clarify these ideas.

Regular Fermi-Dirac or Bose-Einstein Statistics

In the scattering approach, one uses:

$$e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4 \quad ((1a)) \quad \text{and} \quad f(e_1)[1 -/+ f(e_3)] f(e_2) [1 -/+ f(e_4)] = f(e_3) [1 -/+ f(e_1)] f(e_4) [1 -/+ f(e_2)] \quad \text{where } - \text{ represents fermions and } + \text{ bosons} \quad ((1b))$$

Taking \ln of ((1b)) and equating to ((1a)) yields the FD and BE distributions. Actually, one replaces each e_i with $-(1/T)(e_i - u)$ which follows from ((1a)). Thus, the FD and BE distributions may be obtained without counting, entropy or partition functions. For the MB case, one uses $f(e_1)f(e_2) = f(e_3)f(e_4)$.

Alternatively, this may be written as:

$$\ln [f(e_i) / (1 -/+ f(e_i))] = -(e_i - u)/T \quad ((2))$$

It is well known, however, that statistical mechanics texts use counting mechanisms, entropy and partition functions (especially the grand canonical partition function) to obtain the FD and BE distributions. In such a case (grand canonical), one considers for fermions the following:

$$f(e_i) = [0 p^0 + 1 p] / [1 + p] \quad ((2b)) \quad \text{where } p = \exp(-(e_i - u)/T)$$

What seems to happen is that one starts with 1-D configurations or “chains” of particles. At first there are N particles and the total energy is E , so one considers different ways to allocate E . The probability to have a particle with energy e_i is $\exp(-(e_i - u)/T)$. Next one applies the fermion constraint, i.e. restricts oneself to situations where there is only one e_i particle or zero e_i particles in a certain region, say at the beginning of the chain i.e. the chain may start with e_j with

j not i , or with $e_i e_j$ with j not i . These two are acceptable. Thus, one is renormalizing in a sense. The idea of a configuration is consistent with the idea of scattering because for this special case, $f(e_i)$ is the probability to have a particle in state e_i , and also the probability for it to scatter. Thus, there are two probabilities in the picture, but for the "MB" scenario they are equal. We argue this is why configuration and scattering approaches yield identical results (for this special case of regular statistical mechanics).

(Thus, two approaches seem to yield the same result. In a previous note (2), it was shown that for the MB case, one may consider various configurations of single particles in a line as being linked to reactions. If an e_1 and an e_2 are next to each other in a configuration, they may be linked to say an e_3 and e_4 . Thus, there seems to be a way to link configurations with reactions. It should be noted statistical mechanics texts actually count systems in an ensemble in this configuration approach, but we argue that counting may be used also for counting reactions in a single system. Ultimately, $\ln(n!)$ terms are converted using Stirling's approximation to yield a result.)

A second question arises as to the nature of more generalized scattering. For the simple MB case, one may use $f(e_1)f(e_2)$. Imagine there are correlations in the system and one has:

$$e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4 \quad \text{and} \quad g(f(e_1)g(f(e_2))) = g(f(e_3))g(f(e_4)) \quad ((3))$$

One may take \ln of ((3)) and equate again to $-1/T (e_i-u)$. Here $f(e_i)$ represents the number of particles in a state e_i . Using $g(f(e_i))$ seems to indicate that if one specific particle with energy e_i is to scatter, the probability is not proportional to $f(e_i)$, the overall total number of particles, but rather to a function of $f(e_i)$. This seems to indicate a kind of correlation between particles with e_i . Whether such a correlation exists in nature is another question, although there are articles in the literature which argue there various kinds of equilibrium or quasi-equilibrium distributions in nature (experimentally determined) which are not MB.

$$\text{Thus: } g(f(e_i)) = \exp(- (e_i-u)/T) \quad ((4))$$

It seems that $g(f(e_i))$ considered as an entity might map into a counting scheme, but $f(e_i)$ it seems does not. Thus, it seems the idea of considering various allotments of energy to N particles such that the total energy is E and giving each a weight of 1 no longer holds. If it did hold and each "configuration" counted for 1, then $f(e_i)$ would be of the form $\exp(-e_i/T)$, but it is not. Thus, one cannot use a grand canonical approach, it seems, or renormalizing by summing over $n=0$ and $n=1$ to restrict ((4)) to the Fermi Dirac situation.

To generalize ((4)) to the FD or BE situation, we argue one may use:

$$\ln[g(f(e_i)) / (1 \mp f(e_i))] = -(e_i-u)/T \quad (\text{from the scattering approach}) \quad - \text{ for fermions } + \text{ for bosons.}$$

The Question of Entropy

We have argued that the idea of counting configurations, each with a weight of 1, may not hold for generalized statistical mechanics as there seem to be correlations. One may nevertheless “create” an entropy density and hence entropy. This is Kaniadakis entropy (3) and it is created under the restriction that

$$d/df S_d(f) + b(e_i - u) = 0 \quad ((5)) \quad \text{where } b \text{ is a Lagrange multiplier which is } 1/T$$

Thus, $d/df S_d(f)$ where $S_d(f)$ is the entropy density is:

$\ln [g(f)/(1 \mp f)]$ for fermions/bosons or $\ln(g(f))$ ((6)) which follows from the scattering reaction approach.

To obtain $S_d(f)$, one integrates ((6)) over df so that d/df , the inverse operation, cancels the integration.

At first this may seem artificial, yet if one uses $f/(1-f)$ or $f/(1+f)$, this entropy matches that in statistical mechanics texts for fermions and bosons. In texts, this entropy is obtained by counting (i.e. a factorial scheme), which is fine because for this special case $f(e_i)$ is both the probability to be in e_i and the probability to scatter. (Actually, $f(e_i)$ is normalized such that its integral yields N , the total number of particles in the system.) One may use this entropy in $F = E - TS$. The resulting F is of the form of a grand canonical partition function. One may take a derivative with respect to u to obtain the number of particles in a state e_i .

For the more general case, $g(f(e_i))/(1-f(e_i))$ one would also obtain an entropy, the Kaniadakis entropy and from this one may obtain $F = E - TS$. It seems this free energy, however, always has a certain form: (Here we use the fermion $g(f)/(1-f)$ scenario)

$$\begin{aligned} S &= \int d\text{phase space} \int df \ln [g(f)/(1-f)] = \int d\text{phase space} \int df (e_i - u)/T \\ &= E(N) - uN \quad ((6)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{So } F = uN \quad ((7))$$

Now $N = \sum_i n_i$, so if one has $F = \int d\text{phase space} \text{ function}(e_i, u)$ and one takes the derivative d/du , one may find n_i as shown in the case of $f/(1-f)$.

Thus, even generalized statistical mechanics seems to have a “grand canonical partition function”, but it seems not to be linked to counting configurations (i.e. n_i particles with e_i etc).

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that for regular statistical mechanics, the time reversal elastic scattering balance approach seems to be consistent with the counting of configurations (mi particles having energy e_i etc), i.e. with partition functions especially the grand canonical which sums over possible single particle occupation values (e.g. 0 or 1 for fermions). We argue this occurs because the reaction mechanism may be mapped into single chain configurations. The configurations technically count the arrangement of particles with energy e_i etc, while the scattering reaction describes the rate at which reactions occur. These are two very different physical ideas, it seems. For the regular case, $f(e_i)$ represents both as the MB probability for e_1 to scatter with e_2 is $f(e_1)f(e_2)$.

For more generalized statistical mechanics, we argue this mapping no longer holds. For example, if $\ln(g(f(e_i))) = -(e_i - u)/T$, an entity represented by $g(f(e_i))$ may map into a chain, but these entities do not represent the physical particle. Thus, there does not seem to be a reason to develop grand canonical partition functions which count over 0 or 1.

Nevertheless, one may create a Kaniadakis entropy from which one finds $F = E - TS$. The general result is $F = -uN$, where u is the chemical potential. $N = \sum_i n_i$, so if one has a function within an intergral, $d/du F$ seems to yield $f(e_i)$, although one may bypass entropy and F and find $f(e_i)$ directly from the scattering balance which seems to represent the physics of the problem. The Kaniadakis entropy is created from $\ln(g(e_i)/(1 - f))$ by integrating over df so that later when one performs the inverse operation d/df one regains $\ln(g(e_i)/(1 - f))$ which is equated to $-(e_i - u)/T$ (which is added into the problem as a Lagrange multiplier).

References

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